

1 **TITLE**

2 ChatGPT: chances and challenges for dentistry

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18 **KEYWORDS**

19 Artificial intelligence, Dental health services, Evidence-based dentistry, Large language model,
20 Machine learning

21 SUMMARY

22 The artificial intelligence chatbot ChatGPT has generated both huge interest and deep concern
23 since its launch in November 2022. ChatGPT, a large language model (LLM) with a
24 conversational interface, has been trained on vast amounts of human-generated text and has
25 the ability to respond to questions and complete various text-related tasks. The use ChatGPT
26 and similar LLMs in dentistry is unlikely to significantly impact the daily routine of most dental
27 healthcare personnel but could streamline administrative workflows and potentially serve as
28 an additional tool for clinical decision support in the future. However, this is contingent on the
29 availability of comprehensive, up-to-date, and unbiased data. The use of LLMs also causes
30 privacy and cybersecurity concerns. It is therefore crucial to implement robust data protection
31 measures and strong defenses against malicious use of LLMs. Though ChatGPT provides
32 succinct answers to most queries, its lack of reliability, transparency, and up-to-date
33 knowledge compared with conventional search engines is a major drawback, particularly for
34 health-related queries. This article provides an overview of the broad and complex implications
35 that LLMs carry for dentistry. It emphasizes the need for rigorous scientific evaluation and strict
36 legal regulation to realize the potential benefits of LLMs for patient care, education at dental
37 schools, and dental research and to safeguard against the serious risks inherent in such
38 artificial intelligence technologies.

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40

41 **Introduction**

42 Since its release to the public in November 2022, ChatGPT has garnered significant attention
43 and sparked considerable concerns [1]. Within just three months of its launch, the artificial
44 intelligence (AI) chatbot has amassed 100 million users, making it one of the fastest-growing
45 internet applications in history [2].

46 ChatGPT, developed by OpenAI, a US company backed by Microsoft, is a large language
47 model (LLM) with a conversational interface. The ChatGPT chatbot can give answers to the
48 biggest and smallest questions in life, draft passable college essays, job application letters,
49 short stories, sonnets, song lyrics, stir-fry recipes. It is also adept at finding and fixing bugs in
50 computer code [3].

51 ChatGPT can fulfill such text-related tasks because it has been trained on massive amounts
52 of human-generated text, with detailed guidance from AI experts and instructive interactions
53 with volunteers during its development [4]. When replying to a question or prompt, ChatGPT
54 generates statistically likely sequences of words, using statistical patterns learned from vast
55 amounts of textual data. In some sense, this is like predictive text on a cell phone but on a
56 much larger scale and with advanced sophistication.

57 Consider this example. If you ask ChatGPT "How long should I etch lithium disilicate
58 restorations with hydrofluoric acid?", it replies: "20-30 seconds." It provides this answer by
59 analyzing the statistical distribution of words in a huge corpus of English text and determining
60 that "20-30 seconds" is the most probable response. ChatGPT has no actual knowledge of
61 dentistry, you will glad to learn.

62 LLMs such as ChatGPT possess extraordinary capabilities and hold considerable potential for
63 use in dentistry. This article provides a cursory survey of the implications of LLMs for dentistry,
64 including their current limitations and drawbacks.

65 **Everyday working life of dental healthcare personnel**

66 Given that the delivery of dental care heavily relies on in-person communication, clinical and
67 radiographic assessments, and hands-on procedures, LLMs are unlikely to bring significant
68 changes to the daily routine of most dentists, dental assistants, and hygienists. LLMs could,
69 however, change the way dental telemedicine services operate and alter the work of
70 administrative personnel, such as office employees in dental clinics and insurance claims
71 processors.

72 **Routine administrative tasks**

73 LLMs hold promise for streamlining administrative work. In a recent TikTok video, Dr. Clifford
74 Stermer, a rheumatologist based in the US, has demonstrated how the use of ChatGPT can
75 improve the efficiency of writing preauthorization requests for insurance companies [5]. This
76 highlights the potential of LLMs in assisting healthcare personnel to effectively perform routine
77 administrative duties, such as maintaining patient records and submitting insurance
78 reimbursement claims. Some LLMs are also adept at translating languages, making them
79 useful tools for facilitating communication across multiple languages.

80 **Clinical decision support**

81 LLMs have the potential to become an additional tool for clinical decision support. For instance,
82 LLMs that also take into account patients' electronic health record data may soon be used to
83 enhance evidence-based selection of radiological imaging exams [5]. However, the accuracy
84 of LLMs depends on the quality and type of data used in their training, and their usefulness as
85 a clinical support tool is contingent on access to comprehensive, up-to-date, and unbiased
86 data (PATCAS ET AL. 2022). ChatGPT, with its limited knowledge base and lack of internet
87 access, is liable to occasionally produce inaccurate, biased, misleading, or harmful content. It
88 is therefore unsuitable for clinical support today but offers a glimpse into the future of the
89 potential role of LLMs in clinical practice.

90 **Data confidentiality and cybersecurity**

91 The use of LLMs in dentistry raises privacy and security concerns as they may gather personal
92 and medical information. To mitigate these risks, it is crucial to put in place robust data

93 protection measures. The terms of use for ChatGPT allow OpenAI to collect usage data. To
94 ensure patient data privacy, one must therefore enter no patient information into ChatGPT.
95 LLMs also involve dangers for cybersecurity because threat actors may exploit the capabilities
96 of LLMs to create malware and craft phishing messages [6]. The entities involved in building
97 LLMs, including technology companies, research organizations, and governmental agencies,
98 must therefore take proactive measures to prevent malicious use. Additionally, to protect
99 patient data and healthcare providers' technology systems, it is critical to implement and
100 maintain strong defenses against cyberattacks [7, 8].

101 **Online information on dental health**

102 ChatGPT, with its user-friendly dialogue-based interface, provides clear and succinct answers
103 to most queries without the need to navigate to other websites. LLMs such as ChatGPT are
104 therefore predicted to be increasingly used for online queries instead of conventional search
105 engines, such as Baidu, Bing, Google, and Yahoo. However, the accuracy of information
106 provided by ChatGPT is a major concern, particularly for health-related queries. ChatGPT can
107 provide factually incorrect or biased answers with confidence, its knowledge base ends in
108 2021, and it cannot access the internet. Moreover, it is all but impossible to verify the sources
109 of its replies. This lack of reliability, transparency, and up-to-date knowledge is a major
110 drawback compared with conventional search engines. Considering that many people seek
111 medical information online, it is vital to safeguard against inaccurate, outdated, and biased
112 responses from LLMs to health-related queries [9].

113 **Education at dental schools**

114 LLMs present both opportunities and challenges for higher education. It is necessary to adapt
115 some higher education curricula, especially in academic disciplines that strongly rely on written
116 assignments [10–12]. While dental schools, relying less on written assignments, commonly
117 evaluate students through oral exams, multiple-choice tests, practical assessments, and
118 supervised patient treatments, it is important to incorporate education on AI technologies in
119 the curriculum to develop students' understanding of AI applications relevant to dentistry [13].

120

121 **Scientific writing**

122 LLMs can assist authors in improving the fluency, grammar, and spelling of their writing,
123 promoting a level playing field for non-native English speakers looking to publish in English
124 language journals [14]. However, there are serious concerns that the use of LLMs may result
125 in an increase in flawed, faulty, and fabricated research [15–17]. A recent study found that
126 scientific abstracts generated by ChatGPT evaded plagiarism checks and often deceived
127 human reviewers [18]. This highlights the central importance of scientific integrity and thorough
128 peer review in all academic fields, including dental research [19].

129 **Conclusions**

130 It is important to recognize both the potential benefits and potential risks of LLMs such as
131 ChatGPT. In dentistry, LLMs hold promise for improving administrative efficiency and
132 facilitating multilingual communication. In the near future, LLMs may become an additional tool
133 for clinical decision support. However, their usefulness as a tool in dentistry is contingent on
134 the quality and comprehensiveness of data used in training and during user interactions. The
135 use of LLMs in healthcare fields such as dentistry raises privacy and cybersecurity concerns.
136 Effective measures must be taken to mitigate these risks and prevent malicious use. Though
137 ChatGPT offers a user-friendly interface for answering queries, it is currently unsuitable to
138 reliably answer health-related questions and prompts owing to its lack of accuracy,
139 transparency, and up-to-date knowledge. The implications of LLMs for dentistry are far-
140 reaching and complex. Therefore, their use must be approached with caution to ensure the
141 accuracy of information, patient data privacy, and the security of technology systems. Both
142 rigorous scientific evaluation and careful legal regulation are necessary to harness the
143 potential benefits of LLMs for patient care, education, and dental research and to safeguard
144 against the risks inherent in such AI technologies.

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152 repository hold the version of the draft that was revised using ChatGPT [20]. ChatGPT was not
153 used for conceptualization, literature review, data interpretation, and drawing conclusions.

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155 **Conflicts of interest**

156 The authors report no competing financial and/or non-financial interests in relation to the work
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